

Synthesizing Bell States using Universal Quantum Gates

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Abstract

Quantum Computing has experienced a considerable growth in recent times. Though quantum computers have proved to be useful due to applications of Grover's search algorithm and Shor's factorisation algorithm, there exist certain difficulties for implementing scalable quantum computers such as decoherence. Decoherence affects entanglement of two qubits, a phenomenon which perhaps serves as the basis for various crucial applications of quantum computers. Bell state is a pivotal phenomenon based on Qubit entanglement serving useful purpose in Quantum Key Distribution and Quantum Information exchange. Bell state is a disposition in which two qubits are entangled with each other, such that if the state of one qubit changes, the other will also change simultaneously. In this paper we propose a novel algorithm to implement bell states using universal gates only. An error comparison has been performed between the conventional algorithm consisting of Hadamard gate and the proposed algorithm consisting of universal gates. After running for several iterations on a real quantum computing system, the proposed algorithm proves to be more accurate as qubits were observed to collapse in desired states at a greater number of instances than the conventional algorithm.

Keywords: Quantum Information, Bell State, Entanglement, Algorithm Design, Quantum Algorithms

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1. Introduction

1.1 Quantum Computing

Quantum computing is a type of non-classical computing paradigm introduced by Richard Feynman in 1982. It consists of quantum bits, which works on the principles of quantum mechanics. Unlike classical bits, quantum bits (qubits) have the ability to be in the state of both 0 and 1 concurrently. Due to this quantum computers having 'n' qubits can represent 2^n states which provides exponential speed up as compared to classical computers that can only represent $2n$ states while having 'n' classical bits. A qubit can be represented by the following equation

$$|Q\rangle \equiv a|0\rangle + b|1\rangle$$

Where $|0\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$ and $|1\rangle = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}$, a and b are the probabilities of being in the state $|0\rangle$ and $|1\rangle$ respectively, such that $0 \leq a, b \leq 1$ or $a, b \in C$ and $\sqrt{a^2 + b^2} = 1$.

For operating qubits, temperature of absolute zero (i.e. 0 K / -273.15 °C) should be maintained. Even a small deviation from the stated temperature can introduce large errors in our result which may render our results valueless. Since 0 K is an ideal temperature, which is not fully achievable in practice hence same program is run multiple times on a quantum computer and results are evaluated in a holistic manner. A qubit can be adequately represented using a Bloch sphere.

Fig.1 Bloch sphere representation of a qubit

Each point on the sphere represents a qubit state.

Unlike classical computers, in which a bit can be copied from one register to another, quantum bits cannot be copied from one quantum register to another. Other notable difference is searching through an unsorted dataset with a run time complexity of $O(\sqrt{n})$ using Grover's algorithm [2], dissimilar to a complexity of $O(n)$ in classical computers. In 1994 Peter Shor [3] proposed an algorithm for factorizing integers in a polynomial time, which though was carried out on integer 15, but yielded significant results due to huge speed up in the factorization process. Since then persistent research has been carried out in the field and is being reconciled with today's prevailing and prominent fields like encryption and machine learning.

1.2 Bell state

Bell state is a phenomenon introduced by John Stewart Bell in 1964. In this phenomenon two qubits are entangled such that if the state of one qubit is known, the state of the other qubit can be predicted without observing it. It serves useful purposes in various quantum information applications including quantum key distribution [6], quantum cryptography and quantum internet. In conventional methods bell states are synthesized using Hadamard, CNOT gate and Pauli x-gate. In this paper we propose an algorithm for producing bell states using R_x , R_y and CNOT gates. This is quite beneficial for experiments where manufacturing varied quantum gates will not be viable for it. Hadamard gate is used for mapping a qubit from $|n\rangle \rightarrow |k\rangle$ state and vice versa, where $n \in \{0, 1\}$ and $k \in \{+, -\}$. Hadamard gate will be implemented using R_x and R_y gates which are single qubit gates and are used for rotating qubit around x-axis and y-axis respectively on a Bloch sphere. Since both the gates are universal quantum gates, hence the effect of Hadamard gate can be produced by using a series of these gates.

Bell states can be classified into 4 types:

- $|\phi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|00\rangle - |11\rangle)$
- $|\phi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|00\rangle + |11\rangle)$
- $|\psi^-\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|01\rangle - |10\rangle)$
- $|\psi^+\rangle = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (|01\rangle + |10\rangle)$

Generalizing bell state:

$$b(x, y) \equiv \frac{|0,y\rangle + (-1)^x |1,\bar{y}\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}, \quad x, y \in \{0, 1\} \quad (1)$$

A brief introduction to the gates is given below:

- Hadamard gate: it is a n-qubit gate that maps them from $|n\rangle \rightarrow |k\rangle$ state and vice versa, where $n \in \{0, 1\}$ and $k \in \{+, -\}$. It creates a superposition of all states i.e. probability of occurring of each state is equal. Hadamard gate is a Hermitian

operation on a qubit i.e. $H^+ = H$ such that H^+ is the conjugate transpose of H , the operation on a qubit can be stated as

$$H = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{bmatrix}$$

Or

$$|Q\rangle \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{M}} \sum_{x=0}^{M-1} |x\rangle$$

- CNOT (Controlled NOT): is a two-qubit gate in which the value of second qubit is flipped if the first qubit is of the value $|1\rangle$ else remains unchanged.

$$c = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

- X-gate (R_x): is a universal gate that rotates the qubit around x-axis by a phase of θ radians.

$$x(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) & -i \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \\ -i \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix}$$

- Y-gate (R_y): is a universal quantum gate that rotates the qubit around y-axis by a phase of θ radians.

$$y(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) & -\sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \\ \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \end{bmatrix}$$

- Z-gate (R_z): also referred to as phase flip gate, is a quantum gate that rotates the qubit around z-axis by a phase of θ radians. It maps $|+\rangle \rightarrow |-\rangle$ and vice-versa.

$$z(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} \left(\cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) + i \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)\right) & 0 \\ 0 & \left(\cos\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) - i \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)\right) \end{bmatrix}$$

- Pauli-X gate : When qubit is rotated by a phase of π radians along the x-axis, it represents Pauli's x-gate. The operation is similar to NOT, such that it maps $|0\rangle \rightarrow |1\rangle$ and vice versa.

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

- Identity Operator: is used for mapping an algorithm from lower dimensionality (single qubit gates) to higher dimensionality (multi qubit gates)

$$I = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

2. Circuit Implementation

Conventional approach uses Hadamard, CNOT and Pauli-X gate for synthesizing bell states, since CNOT is a universal quantum gate, hence we need to replace the two remaining gates i.e. Hadamard and Pauli-X with a combination of universal gates. Bell state can be produced using the following equation

$$B \equiv CNOT \otimes (H \otimes I)(|k'\rangle \otimes |k\rangle) \quad (2)$$

Where $k, k' \in \{0, 1\}$ and \otimes is the tensor product

Hadamard operation can be synthesized by a rotation of π radians by z-axis followed by a rotation of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ radians by y-axis, Therefore

$$H \equiv R_{y(\frac{\pi}{2})} * R_z(\pi) \quad (3)$$

Where * represents matrix multiplication.

Since R_z is not the required gate, hence it should be decomposed into a combination of R_x and R_y . Therefore R_z can be represented as:

$$R_z \equiv R_{y(-\frac{\pi}{2})} * R_{x(\frac{\pi}{2})} * R_{y(\frac{\pi}{2})} \quad (4)$$

Substituting eq. (4) into eq. (3)

$$H \equiv R_{y(\frac{\pi}{2})} * R_{y(-\frac{\pi}{2})} * R_{x(\frac{\pi}{2})} * R_{y(\frac{\pi}{2})} \quad (5)$$

Substituting eq. (5) into eq. (2)

$$B \equiv CNOT \otimes \left(\left(R_{y(\frac{\pi}{2})} * \left(R_{y(-\frac{\pi}{2})} * R_{x(\pi)} * R_{y(\frac{\pi}{2})} \right) \right) \otimes I \right) (|k'\rangle \otimes |k\rangle) \quad (6)$$

Hence eq. (6) is the required result as now the equation consists of only CNOT, R_x and R_y gates.

3. Experimental Methods

For all the bell states both the algorithms i.e. consisting of Hadamard gates and universal gates have been tested on a 2 qubit IBM-Q system. Since for evaluating the results on a quantum computer, an algorithm is run several times and the outcomes are then observed for correctness, hence a set of iterations (or shots) have been applied for each state and outcomes for the same has been observed. Consider iterations carried out on the algorithms as S, such that $S \in \{10, 25, 50, 75, 100\}$.

Error for each iteration has been calculated by the given formula

$$\text{Percentage of error} = \frac{\sum(\text{Occurrence of undesirable states})}{\text{Total number of occurrences}} * 100$$

4. Results

Following graphs represent the plot of iterations versus error having plots for conventional algorithm (using Hadamard gate) and the proposed algorithm (using universal gates). The dotted lines represent the results for proposed algorithm while smooth curve represents the results for conventional algorithm.

Fig.2.1 Error comparison for bell state ψ^-

[Fig.2.2 Error comparison for bell state ϕ^-]

[Fig.2.3 Error comparison for bell state ψ^+]

[Fig.2.4 Error comparison for bell state ϕ^+]

5. Discussions and Conclusions

It can be observed from the Fig. 2 that the proposed algorithm proves to be less error prone as compared to the conventional algorithm. Even though the complexity of circuit increases with the proposed algorithm still it proves to be more efficient when ran over a range of iterations.

The algorithm can be improvised further by decreasing the complexity of the circuit and implementing a suitable quantum error correction algorithm for averting the collapse of qubits to an undesirable state under observation.

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